

A Model Programme for Chemical Education in India

A. K. GHOSE, RAM LAKHAN GUPTA and R. BALAJI RAO*

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 18 February 1994, accepted 2 March 1995

Chemical education in India is being evolved under severe constraints. A rigid university system which tends to compartmentalise education into impractical capsules of specialisations with no facility for cross-movement of students, teachers and ideas, a trend to divide education into professional and nonprofessional courses (as if music is not professional) and a total exclusion of industries from the arena of course planning and training are the root causes for the maladies that have afflicted the Indian university system. So far we have been indulging in fragmented (and often cosmetic) changes which has only resulted in the loss of the wood for the trees. Hence the question of chemical education should be addressed as a whole and not restricted to isolated changes or introduction of a few select (popular sounding) new courses. Since changing the university system in India is a larger question beyond the purview of the chemistry fraternity alone, it is desirable to set our house in order within the available frame.

If the purpose of higher education is to train manpower for higher levels of employment in industry and research, the need for job orientation of chemical education cannot be overstressed. Once the question of job orientation is raised, the obvious point that comes up is whether a chemist is a professional and if so should the manpower training be in the lines of a professional course as against a training in pure sciences, wherein the motto is knowledge and enquiry for the pleasure of learning. Chemistry occupies a unique position amongst sciences. The chemistry cauldron has given birth to several professional courses. This field still continues to bring forth new professions. The unfortunate inclusion of chemistry under pure sciences in our university system has resulted in total isolation of chemical education from the industry which has been the main beneficiary of this mother science. Given the inflexible Indian university system, we have to find ways of introducing a corrective step to incorporate continued interaction of the teaching institutes with industries. A model framework is presented below as a guideline for evolving a more flexible pattern of university-industry interactions for teaching and research, with special reference to chemistry.

Teaching programmes

A five-year college course could be tentatively divided into suitable segments (2 + 1 + 2) and the employment potential at each level could be clearly defined. For example, the first and second year courses could be a thorough back-

ground course with a foundation in computer techniques. A Diploma at this level could equip the student for middle school science teaching, laboratory technician jobs in industries and R & D units, marketing and administrative jobs. The third year degree course (B.Sc. Honours) could cater to the needs of high school teaching, research technician jobs and production chemists jobs in industries. The fourth and fifth year courses could aim at training in instrument operation, quality control, research assistance in R & D laboratories and teaching in colleges. The research oriented training at Ph.D. levels could generate manpower for higher level employments.

The *core courses* could run through the first two and a half years. To meet the job aspiration of the students, *elective topics* could be introduced from the third year onwards. The elective topics could be programmed and conducted by the university teachers and scientists from the participating industries. After completion of the *core courses*, there could be free movement of students from one institute to another to allow the development of specialised courses, depending upon the teaching potential of the institutes. Award of the Degree would be made only when the student has completed the required *core courses* and *elective courses*. The *core/elective* courses should be directly correlated with the proposed job potential of the Diploma/Degree awarded.

The practical courses should include a core training in the teaching institute and special training courses at the participating industries or research laboratories. Keeping in mind the cost, the utility and the craftsmanship factors in mind, the training in the classical techniques should be restricted to the essential minimum with emphasis on the methodology rather than an overemphasis on perfection through repetition.

Some major departures are suggested here keeping in mind the demands of the fast changing job markets. A student should be permitted to acquire multiple specialisations, if he so desires (and he has the requisite foundation *core courses*). Such a facility would enable a student to meet the changing demands of the job market. After completion of the *core courses*, the student should be free to move to other teaching institutes to study *electives* of his choice, rather than be limited to the *electives* available at the parent institute. The national laboratories and industries could play an active role in the special training courses. A training programme and a dissertation should form an integral part of the III, IV and V year courses. The Pooja and

summer vacations could be gainfully utilised for such special training courses. This system involves coursewise admission. The fee structure could be made more realistic at this level. The rush for each special course would depend on the employment potential and not the fee payable. The universities should introduce special provisions for reorientation programmes to suit the changing needs of the job market and career advancement of an individual. The suggested model is outlined below.

Higher education in chemistry

Outline of teaching programme for [2 + 1 + 2] followed by research degrees :

Unit = 2 Lectures/week

First two years :

Course (Units/year) : Chemistry (3), two other science subjects (3 each), introduction to computer techniques (1)

Practical training in Science subjects (6 labs/week)

Job potential : Middle school teaching (B.Ed.), shift chemists, laboratory technicians in R & D centres, librarian (D.Lib.), sales, administration (junior cadre)

Degree awarded : A Diploma in Sciences

Third year : (> 60% in the above course, Career improvement for employed people with minimum qualification)

Course (units/year) : Chemistry Major

Core courses (9) : General chemistry courses, computer techniques in chemistry, applied spectroscopy, frontier areas/job oriented courses

Practicals (6 labs/week) : In the above areas

Electives (4) : Industrial processes, environmental chemistry, pharmaceutical chemistry, quality control techniques etc.

Practicals (4) : Project during vacation, tours etc.

Job potential : High school teaching (B.Ed.), industrial production/quality control chemists), R & D and teaching units as laboratory assistant, clinical pathology

Degree awarded : B.Sc. (Honours)

Fourth and fifth years (>60% at the Honours level. Career improvement for employed graduates with above minimum)

Course (units)

Core courses (9) : Advanced topics in inorganic, organic, physical and analytical chemistry

Practicals (6 lab days) : R & D techniques in the above areas

Electives (4) : Special lecture courses by experts

Practicals : Industrial and R & D training projects during vacations for one to three months

Job potential : Instrument operators, senior technical and research assistant, teaching upto B.Sc. (University administration training), self-employment

Degree awarded : M.Sc.

Research Degrees (M.Phil. and Ph.D.)

Course work and research thesis

Job potential : Scientists, P. G. teaching, high level technical and management jobs

Programme management

The Chemical Societies should play an important role in planning the manpower training programmes for the chemistry profession through an apex body for professional chemists (which shall be different from the association of chemical engineers). This association of professional chemists should propose a model syllabus for the above programme, review the curriculum and laboratory facilities of all the teaching units in the country, award grade points on a 10-point scale (with highest as 10 and lowest as 1 and a programme equivalent to the above syllabus as seven), derecognise units with grade points 1-3 and provide advice to all units in upgrading their courses. This apex body could also function as link between teaching institutes and industrial R & D units and act as a watchdog to protect the interests of the profession. It shall not interfere with the functioning of the teaching units.

The individual teaching units could adopt the syllabus proposed by the apex body, with minimum modifications to suit its special location and teaching facilities available. In our opinion, a uniform syllabus is neither feasible nor desirable. Within a given framework, teaching should evolve as a dynamic force engaged in the shaping of the profession and the society it serves.

Conclusion

The above mentioned programme could easily be adopted by individual teaching institutes with local modifications. It does not require any major inputs in terms of infrastructure of manpower. The vast expertise available in the national laboratories and industrial units could be easily tapped to supplement the local expertise and facilities. After all, these teaching units produce manpower mainly for the industries. The reverse flow of expertise into teaching units would certainly make the graduates more employable than at present. The teaching units would also be liberated from the limitations of facilities which is the main cause for the limited teaching programmes in our teaching units. Such interactive programmes would also lead to progressive appreciation of the expertise and research problems/results available at the participating centres thus creating a right atmosphere for mutual growth.